

IN THE BEGINNING OF THE TWENTIETH CENTURY, THE PEOPLE OF
TURKESTAN IN THE ROLE OF THE SOCIAL SUPPORT OF THE
CHARITABLE SOCIETY

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Abstract: *This article talks about the charitable societies established in Turkestan and their role and importance in social and spiritual support of the people of the region.*

Key words: *youth, savings, modernization, reform, future.*

The political, economic and spiritual life that arose as a product of colonialism and great nationalism policies formed the ground and reasons for the struggle for independence. Social and political movements that occurred at the beginning of the 20th century meant that in the minds of the local population, it is necessary to fight against oppression, and it is no longer possible to live in the old way. During this period, the activity of enlighteners was clearly demonstrated. The processes of establishing new method schools, press activities and articles encouraging the people to fight for their independence had a great impact on the growth of the spiritual consciousness of the population.

The ground and conditions that served as the main factor in the emergence of the Jadidism movement as a major socio-political force in Turkestan itself had been reached. Uzbek Jadids paid serious attention to the public education of Turkestan. In this field, the well-known mudarris and enlightener Munavvar Qari Abdurashidkhanov has made a great contribution. In 1909, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, in cooperation with his professional friends Abdulla Avloni, Ubaydulla Asadullakhojaev, Tashpolatbek Norbotabekov and others, organized “Jamiyati Khairiya” under the chairmanship of a rich man from Tashkent. Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov and his comrades are not limited to helping poor and sick people and students through the society, but also send students to higher educational institutions in Russia and Turkey. Abdurahman Akbarov, an old artist belonging to the Munavvarqori group, remembers such an event in his memory: “Munavvarqori, who was the main leader of the group, came to the meeting of the group one day and said: “Some of the intelligent young people should be sent to Germany to be educated.” spoke. About 15 days later, a large gathering took place at the house of Kattakhoja Khojaev for the second time. The most famous poets of Tashkent gathered at this meeting. Among them, Orifkhojaboy, Saidkarimboy, Kamiljonboy chaifurush, Asil elder, Baqijonboy and others. There were 50-60 people gathered here. The sons of Munavvarqori and Ilhom samovarchi and Murodhoja Salihoja showed more initiative in organizing this. After everyone has

gathered, the meeting will be opened and Munavvarqori will be the first to speak. Munavvar Qori: “We really need to send the children of Uzbek intellectuals to Germany for education. He made a long speech with the words, “If the children are educated, they will be able to serve the nation”.

In fact, the first New Methodist school was opened in Khiva on November 10, 1904, with the support of the newly established “Jamiyati Khairiya” as a consistent continuation of the reforms carried out by the Jadids. In 1908, “Bukharai Sharif Company” was established and engaged in publishing textbooks and selling books. In the same year, the Jadids established an educational society in Bukhara – “Tarbiyai atfol” (“Children’s education”). With the efforts and support of the charitable society, 14 young people from Bukhara and Turkestan studied in Istanbul in 1908, 15 in 1911, and 30 in 1912. At that time, the number of children from other countries in Germany was: 10,000 Russians, 4,000 Japanese, 2,000 Ottoman Turks, 300 Egyptians, 500 Indians, 200 Arabs, 500 Iranians, 500 Afghans, and 70 students from all over Turkestan.

Based on the support of “Tarbiyai atfol”, Fitrat’s works “Munozara”, “Hind sayyohi khazana” and “Sayha”, as well as Sadriddin Ainiy, Abdulvahid. The books of Burkhanov and others were published in Turkey and distributed in Turkestan.

In 1909, the organization of charity funds became active. Abdulla Awlani also created “Jamiyati Khairiya” and educated orphans. In 1909, “Jamiyati Imdodiya” was established by Munavvarqori in Tashkent. He also helped poor and weak students, helped to send young people to study abroad. “Kumak” charitable society was also established in Tashkent in 1909, its founders were Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Nizomgori Hasanov, Abdulla Avloni, Basharulla Asadullakhojaev and Tashkhoja Tuyokboyev. “Kumak” provides great support to modern schools and has helped to send talented young people to study abroad. Education abroad has made a radical change in the outlook of young people. First of all, they had to get acquainted with the achievements and experiences of Germany, the most developed country in Western Europe at that time, and on this basis, save the country from economic and cultural backwardness. Indeed, the prospects of any country often depend on highly educated activists who are sufficiently prepared to serve its interests.

If the country of Turkestan really wants to achieve the development of its national autonomy in the future, then in the near future it will be armed with high-level modern sciences, which will be able to solve the big tasks in front of its indigenous population.

The only way out of these difficulties is to immediately send the most talented young people of Turkestan abroad, and give them the opportunity to receive secondary and higher education.

From the above, it can be concluded that enlightened people who correctly understood the socio-political situation in the region at the beginning of the 20th century said that all areas of society need radical reform, and for this, modern-minded scientists who are well-versed in Western European science are definitely needed. Those who understand. In a short period of time, they managed to organize a number

of charitable societies for their study abroad. However, the representatives of the former totalitarian regime pursued the policy of keeping the region under their control and destroying the representatives of the intelligentsia who could fight for the freedom of Turkestan with various tricks.

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